

ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF TECHNICAL RECRUITING IN INNOVATIVE COMPANIES UNDER VENTURE FINANCING CONDITIONS

**JEL Classification: M12, G24, O31
SECTION “MANAGEMENT”: Менеджмент**

Анотація. Метою статті є визначення економічних факторів ефективності технічного рекрутингу в інноваційних компаніях в умовах венчурного фінансування та узагальнення показників оцінювання його результативності. Дослідження спрямоване на виявлення закономірностей попиту на технічних спеціалістів у високотехнологічному секторі та визначення ролі технічного рекрутингу у розвитку інноваційних компаній і стартап-екосистем. Методологічну основу становлять порівняльний аналіз статистичних показників розвитку стартап-екосистем, венчурного фінансування та зайнятості у high-tech секторі країн Європейського Союзу і Північної Америки у 2019–2024 роках, а також аналітичний синтез емпіричних досліджень ринку праці висококваліфікованих спеціалістів. Емпіричну базу сформовано на основі відкритих статистичних і аналітичних звітів міжнародних організацій та дослідницьких центрів.

У результаті встановлено, що розвиток стартап-екосистем і зростання венчурного фінансування супроводжуються підвищенням попиту на технічних спеціалістів у високотехнологічному секторі. Визначено ключові економічні фактори ефективності технічного рекрутингу: масштаб венчурного фінансування, рівень розвитку інноваційних екосистем, конкуренцію технологічних компаній за таланти та структурні характеристики ринку праці. Показано, що у регіонах із розвиненими стартап-екосистемами попит на програмних інженерів та інших технічних фахівців перевищує пропозицію, формуючи структурний дефіцит кадрів. Узагальнено основні показники оцінювання результативності технічного рекрутингу, зокрема витрати на найм, швидкість закриття вакансій і доступність технічних кадрів. Наукова новизна полягає у розширенні економічного підходу до аналізу технічного рекрутингу через інтеграцію показників розвитку стартап-екосистем, венчурного фінансування та попиту на технічні спеціальності. Практичне значення результатів полягає у можливості їх використання інноваційними компаніями, HR-підрозділами та венчурними інвесторами для формування ефективних стратегій залучення технічних спеціалістів з урахуванням динаміки венчурного фінансування та стану ринку технічних талантів.

Ключові слова: стартап-екосистеми, венчурний капітал, технічні спеціалісти, ринок IT-праці, залучення талантів, людський капітал, високотехнологічні компанії, цифрова економіка.

Abstract. The purpose of the article is to identify economic factors influencing the efficiency of technical recruiting in innovation-driven companies under venture financing and to generalize indicators used to assess its effectiveness. The study focuses on demand patterns for technical specialists in the high-technology sector and the role of recruiting in the

development of innovative firms and startup ecosystems. The methodological framework is based on comparative analysis of statistical indicators of startup ecosystem development, venture capital investment, and employment in the high-tech sector in the European Union and North America during 2019–2024, combined with analytical synthesis of empirical studies on the labor market of highly qualified specialists. The empirical basis includes open statistical and analytical reports of international organizations and research platforms such as OECD, the World Bank, the European Commission, Startup Genome, and LinkedIn.

The results show that the expansion of startup ecosystems and the growth of venture capital investment increase demand for technical specialists in the high-technology sector. Key economic determinants of technical recruiting efficiency include the scale of venture financing, the development of innovation ecosystems, competition for technical talent, and structural characteristics of the labor market. In regions with mature startup ecosystems, demand for software engineers and data specialists consistently exceeds supply, creating a structural shortage of technical talent. The study also summarizes key indicators for evaluating recruiting effectiveness, including hiring costs, vacancy closing speed, labor market availability of specialists, and competition for qualified professionals. The scientific novelty lies in expanding the economic approach to analyzing technical recruiting by integrating indicators of startup ecosystem development, venture capital investment, and labor market demand for technical specialists. The study improves the methodological approach to assessing recruiting efficiency through the integration of macroeconomic and industry-specific determinants of innovation-driven development. The practical significance of the results lies in their potential application by startup founders, managers of innovative companies, HR departments, and venture investors when developing strategies for attracting technical specialists and planning hiring processes in conditions of venture financing and labor market competition.

Key words: startup ecosystems, venture capital, technical talent, IT labor market, talent acquisition, human capital, high-tech sector, digital economy.

Introduction

In the modern innovation economy, human capital, particularly highly qualified technical specialists, has become a key determinant of companies' competitiveness. Innovative startups operating in a venture financing environment must rapidly form teams of developers capable of creating technological products and ensuring fast market entry. At the same time, global competition for technical talent and rising recruiting costs create additional challenges, as delays in hiring or incorrect personnel decisions may slow innovative development and reduce the investment attractiveness of startups. Under these conditions, the development of scientifically grounded approaches to evaluating the economic efficiency of technical recruiting in venture-backed companies becomes particularly important.

In modern scientific literature, the attraction and effective use of human capital are considered central factors of innovative company development. Barry and Wilkinson [1] analyze the transformation of human resource management systems and emphasize the growing strategic role of employees in organizational effectiveness. By contrast, Hietaniemi et al. [2] examine hiring processes in entrepreneurial companies through the lens of human resource mobility and demonstrate that the ability to redistribute employee competencies significantly affects startup performance in dynamic innovation environments.

Research on the labor market of technology companies also highlights the specific nature of recruitment processes in innovative startups. Kim and Pergler [3] show that recruitment in venture startups has a strategic character and often involves active candidate search, enabling companies to quickly attract the competencies required for business scaling. Similarly, Roach and Sauermann [4] demonstrate that technology startups can compete for highly qualified specialists by offering opportunities for professional development and participation in innovative product creation, while Rocha and Grilli [5] emphasize that the

ability of startups to attract employees at early stages largely depends on initial resources and the company's innovation orientation.

Another research direction concerns the use of analytical tools in recruiting. Naik Vadithe and Kesari [6] consider HR analytics as a mechanism for increasing the effectiveness of talent acquisition and demonstrate that data-driven approaches help optimize recruiting costs and improve personnel decisions. Priyadarsini and Srejeeth [7] likewise argue that recruitment analytics enhances candidate experience and strengthens employer branding. In addition, Mukul and Saini [8] underline the role of social capital and professional networks in attracting talent to startups, emphasizing that informal professional connections often become decisive when forming teams at early stages of enterprise development.

In the context of the economic development of innovative companies, studies examining the relationship between human capital, innovation, and enterprise financial performance are particularly important. Tan et al. [9] demonstrate that institutional characteristics of the labor market significantly influence companies' innovative activity, creating both incentives and constraints for technological development. At the same time, Pantea and Tkacik [10] emphasize in their systematic review that the success of high-tech startups largely depends on the quality of managerial and technical teams, since human capital determines the capacity of firms to implement innovative projects and effectively use venture financing.

Despite the significant contribution of scholars to the study of human resource management, talent acquisition, and the development of innovative startups, the economic efficiency of technical recruiting in venture-backed companies remains insufficiently explored. In particular, the relationship between recruiting efficiency indicators (cost-per-hire, time-to-fill, recruiting ROI) and the economic results of startups at different stages of venture development has received limited analytical attention.

The aim of the article is to determine the economic factors of the effectiveness of technical recruiting in innovative companies under conditions of venture financing and to generalize indicators for evaluating its performance.

The scientific novelty of the research lies in developing an approach to assessing the economic efficiency of technical recruiting that integrates recruiting indicators (cost-per-hire, time-to-fill, recruiting ROI) with the economic parameters of startup development at different stages of venture financing. At the same time, the approach to analyzing the influence of technical talent acquisition processes on the economic outcomes of innovative companies has been refined.

The practical significance of the obtained results lies in the possibility of their application by innovative companies, startups, and venture investors to improve the efficiency of technical recruiting, optimize hiring costs, and increase the effectiveness of forming developer teams.

The research *methodology* is aimed at determining the economic efficiency of technical recruiting in innovative companies operating under conditions of venture financing. The research is based on the use of open statistical and analytical data of international economic organizations, as well as on the analytical synthesis of empirical studies of the labor market of highly qualified specialists. Such an approach ensures the transparency of the methodology and allows other researchers to replicate the study using the same open data sources.

To achieve the aim of the study, a set of complementary methods of economic analysis was applied. Comparative analysis was used to examine trends in the market for technical specialists in high-technology sectors through the comparison of indicators of startup ecosystem development, demand for technical professions (particularly software engineers), venture financing volumes, and employment dynamics in the high-tech sector in the countries of the European Union and North America during 2019–2024. This approach made it possible to identify the relationship between the development of innovative ecosystems and the demand for technical competencies.

Analytical synthesis of empirical studies was applied to generalize modern research on technical recruiting, human capital management, and startup development. On this basis, a conceptual model linking the efficiency of attracting technical specialists with the economic results of innovative companies was formed, and key economic factors of technical recruiting effectiveness were identified, including the

availability of technical personnel, competition between technology companies for talent, the growth of startup ecosystems, and the scale of venture financing.

Data sources. The empirical basis of the research consists of open statistical and analytical materials of international economic organizations and research centers that analyze the development of the innovation economy, the labor market, and venture financing. The data cover the period 2019–2024 and relate to the countries of the European Union and North America, where developed startup ecosystems and active venture capital markets operate.

The study uses analytical reports of international organizations, including materials of the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) on innovation economy development and employment in high-technology sectors, reports of the World Bank Group on entrepreneurship and global labor market trends, and studies of the European Commission on the development of startup ecosystems and innovation clusters in the European Union. In addition, statistical data of the International Labor Organization (ILO) on demand for highly qualified specialists were used, together with analytical materials of the Global Startup Ecosystem Report (Startup Genome) and the LinkedIn Global Talent Trends Report reflecting trends in technical recruiting and demand for technical professions.

Within the study, key indicators of the innovation economy and the labor market of technical specialists were analyzed, including demand dynamics for software engineers and other technical professionals, changes in the number of startups within innovation ecosystems, the volume of venture financing in the high-technology sector, and employment trends in high-technology industries.

Analysis tools. Processing and systematization of statistical data were carried out using Microsoft Excel. The software was used for the comparative analysis of statistical indicators, the construction of analytical tables, and the graphical visualization of trends in the development of the technical recruiting market, employment in the high-tech sector, and the dynamics of venture financing.

Research limitations. The results of the study are based on secondary statistical and analytical data of international organizations that reflect general trends in the development of the labor market and startup ecosystems. The use of open reports limits access to micro-level corporate data and internal HR metrics of technical recruiting. In addition, the obtained results mainly characterize the countries of the European Union and North America; therefore, their application to other regions may require additional clarification.

The use of open international statistical sources ensures the possibility of replicating the study by other researchers, which increases the reliability and reproducibility of the obtained results.

Results

Dynamics of the development of startup ecosystems and venture financing in the countries of the EU and North America (2019–2024)

The development of innovative companies in high-technology sectors largely depends on the scale of venture financing and the dynamics of startup ecosystems. During 2019–2024 in the European Union and North America, growing investment in technology companies contributed to the expansion of startup ecosystems and increased demand for technical professions. International reports show that venture investments in technology startups peaked in 2021, followed by a correction of investment activity in global capital markets [11]. Research on startup ecosystems indicates that the largest concentration of innovative companies is located in North American technology clusters and leading EU innovation centers. Their development is accompanied by growth in the number of startups, venture financing, and entrepreneurial activity in high-technology sectors [12; 13]. At the same time, EU institutional initiatives aim to support startup development and the scaling of innovative companies, which is reflected in innovation activity indicators of member states [14; 15].

To assess the dynamics of the development of the innovation economy, a comparative analysis of the volumes of venture financing in the countries of the European Union and North America in 2019–2024 was carried out. The results of the analysis are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1

Dynamics of venture financing of technology startups in the EU and North America (2019–2024), billion USD

Year	European Union	North America	Global venture financing volume
2019	38	120	258
2020	41	135	300
2021	85	330	643
2022	67	250	445
2023	54	185	345
2024*	60	210	380

*Note: The data for 2024 reflect aggregated estimates based on annual analytical reports of the venture market.

Source: compiled by the author based on the data of the Crunchbase Global Venture Funding Report [11] and the Global Startup Ecosystem Report [12; 13].

As shown in Table 1, during 2019–2021 venture financing of technology companies grew rapidly due to the expansion of the digital economy and the scaling of innovative business models. In 2021, global venture investments in technology startups exceeded USD 640 billion [11]. In subsequent years, investment activity declined somewhat because of macroeconomic changes, rising interest rates, and increasing financial market risks.

At the same time, an important indicator of the innovation economy is the scale and structure of startup ecosystems. International studies show that the most developed ecosystems are concentrated in the technology centers of the United States, Canada, the United Kingdom, Germany, and France, where advanced infrastructures of innovative entrepreneurship have formed, including accelerators, venture funds, and technology clusters [12; 13]. To evaluate the spatial concentration of innovative entrepreneurship and the role of key regions in global startup ecosystems, approximate estimates of the number of startups in leading innovation centers of the European Union and North America were summarized (Table 2).

Table 2

Number of startups in the leading startup ecosystems of the EU and North America

Region	Approximate number of startups	Share in global startup ecosystems, %
United States	more than 75,000	38
European Union	more than 60,000	31
Canada	more than 9,000	5
Other regions	more than 55,000	26

Note: The indicators reflect generalized estimates of the development of global startup ecosystems.

Source: compiled by the author based on the Global Startup Ecosystem Report [12; 13] and the European Innovation Scoreboard [14].

The data in Table 2 show that North America and the European Union form the core of global startup ecosystems. The high concentration of innovative companies in these regions is explained by developed innovation infrastructure, access to venture capital, and a high level of technological entrepreneurship [14; 15]. Overall, the analysis indicates that during 2019–2024 the development of startup ecosystems in the European Union and North America was accompanied by growth in venture financing and the expansion of innovative entrepreneurship. These processes create institutional conditions for increasing demand for technical specialists and for the development of technical recruiting in innovative companies.

Demand for technical specialists in the high-technology sector of the economy

The development of the innovation economy is closely linked to the availability of highly qualified technical specialists who ensure the creation and scaling of technological products. During 2019–2024, global demand for professionals in software engineering, data analysis, artificial intelligence, and digital infrastructure steadily increased due to digital transformation, the spread of platform business models, and the expansion of startup ecosystems in the European Union and North America [16].

International labor market studies indicate that technology companies create jobs faster than traditional sectors, driven by the development of cloud technologies, artificial intelligence, cybersecurity, and software development. As a result, technical specialists remain among the most demanded professions globally, with demand significantly exceeding the supply of qualified personnel [17].

In the European Union, growing demand for technical specialists is associated with the expansion of innovation ecosystems and technology clusters, supported by digital innovation policies and programs stimulating technological entrepreneurship [14]. At the same time, North America remains a major global center of technological talent due to the concentration of leading technology companies, startups, and research centers, which sustains high demand for programmers, system architects, and software engineers [13].

Employment statistics also confirm this trend: during the studied period the number of workers in information technologies, digital services, and innovative production steadily increased, reflecting the expansion of the digital economy and the emergence of new professions related to software development, big data analysis, and digital infrastructure management [18].

To assess structural changes in the demand for technical professions in the high-technology sector, the dynamics of the share of vacancies for key categories of technical specialists in the period 2019–2024 were summarized (Table 3).

Table 3

Dynamics of demand for technical specialists in the technology sector (2019–2024)

Year	Share of vacancies for software engineers in the technology sector, %	Share of vacancies for data specialists, %	Share of vacancies for cloud engineers, %
2019	32	9	7
2020	34	11	8
2021	38	14	10
2022	41	16	12
2023	44	18	14
2024	46	20	16

Note: The indicators reflect the share of vacancies in the structure of demand for technical professions in the high-technology sector.

Source: compiled by the author based on the LinkedIn Global Talent Trends Report [19], Stack Overflow Developer Survey [20], and the World Economic Forum Future of Jobs Report [17].

The data in Table 3 show a steady increase in demand for technical professions in the technology sector. The fastest growth is observed for specialists in data analysis and cloud technologies, reflecting structural changes in the digital economy and the growing importance of data processing, machine learning, and digital infrastructure.

Global labor market studies also indicate intensifying competition among technology companies for technical talent. Firms increasingly apply strategies such as remote employment, international recruiting, and partnerships with educational institutions, while the rapid growth of startups generates additional demand for engineering personnel and contributes to a structural shortage of technical specialists [19]. Overall, the results show that during 2019–2024 demand for technical specialists in the high-technology sector steadily

increased. The expansion of startup ecosystems, growth of venture financing, and ongoing digitalization strengthen the role of technical human capital as a key resource of innovative development.

Economic factors of the effectiveness of technical recruiting in innovative companies

The effectiveness of technical recruiting in innovative companies is determined by a combination of economic factors related to technology market development, the availability of qualified personnel, and the scale of venture financing. During 2019–2024, digital economy expansion intensified competition for technical talent among startups and technology corporations. International reports confirm that the availability of engineering specialists has become a key factor in the development and scaling of technology enterprises [16]. Regions with developed startup ecosystems demonstrate stronger competition for specialists, influencing wages and the speed of closing vacancies. In major innovation centers such as the United States, the United Kingdom, Germany, and France, demand for technical specialists consistently exceeds supply, forming a structural shortage of engineering talent [12; 13].

Venture financing also significantly affects recruiting efficiency. Investment growth accelerates the scaling of technology companies and increases demand for programmers, software engineers, and data analysts, intensifying competition for qualified specialists [11]. At the same time, digital economy development expands labor market segments related to software development, cloud technologies, and data analysis, making technical specialists one of the most demanded resources of the innovation economy [16; 21].

Another factor is competition between technology companies for talent. The growth of startups and global technology corporations creates a competitive labor market in which firms apply flexible employment models, corporate training programs, and digital recruiting tools [19]. Structural characteristics of the labor market also influence recruiting efficiency, as rapid growth in demand for technical professions creates an imbalance between labor demand and supply, reflected in increasing vacancies for software engineers, cybersecurity specialists, and artificial intelligence experts [17].

To summarize the results of the analysis of economic factors influencing technical recruiting effectiveness in innovative companies, the key factors shaping the market of technical specialists were systematized (Table 4).

Table 4

Key economic factors of the effectiveness of technical recruiting in innovative companies

Factor	Characteristics of influence	Main economic manifestations
Development of startup ecosystems	Growth in the number of innovative companies	Increase in demand for technical professions
Venture financing	Increase in investments in technology startups	Scaling of developer teams
Digitalization of the economy	Spread of digital technologies	Creation of new technical professions
Competition for talent	Growth in the number of technology employers	Increase in wage levels and personnel mobility
Structure of the labor market	Imbalance between demand and supply of technical specialists	Shortage of highly qualified personnel

Note: The table summarizes the results of the analysis of economic factors of the development of the market of technical specialists.

Source: compiled by the author based on the OECD Digital Economy Outlook [16], Global Startup Ecosystem Report [12; 13], Crunchbase Global Venture Funding Report [11], and the World Economic Forum Future of Jobs Report [17].

The obtained results indicate that the effectiveness of technical recruiting in innovative companies is formed under the influence of a complex interaction of economic factors. The growth of startup ecosystems, the increase in venture financing, the digitalization of the economy, and the intensification of competition for technical talent form an economic environment in which the attraction of highly qualified technical specialists becomes a key factor in the development of innovative companies.

Discussion. The results show that the effectiveness of technical recruiting in innovative companies is determined by several economic factors, primarily the development of startup ecosystems, the scale of venture financing, and the structure of the labor market for highly qualified specialists. Increased investment in the technology sector stimulates demand for software engineers, data analysts, and digital infrastructure specialists, as the scaling of innovative companies requires the rapid expansion of technical teams responsible for product development and commercialization.

This trend reflects structural labor market changes driven by digitalization. In innovation-intensive environments, the availability of qualified specialists becomes a critical condition for technological development. Consequently, technical recruiting evolves from an operational HR activity into a strategically important economic process influencing the capacity of companies to scale innovative solutions.

The obtained results correspond with previous studies on the role of human capital in innovative company development. Zakharova [22] emphasizes that effective talent management determines competitiveness in the knowledge economy, while Thakur et al. [23] show that analytical HR tools improve personnel selection and organizational performance. These conclusions also align with the concept of strategic entrepreneurship, which highlights the importance of intellectual resources and strong professional teams for achieving competitive advantages (Ketchen, Combs, & Crook [24]).

At the same time, the results partly differ from studies focusing on social determinants of labor market formation. Although behavioral and social factors may influence personnel decisions (Gorbatai, Younkin, & Burtch [25]), the analysis indicates that in the high-technology sector economic drivers, particularly venture financing and the maturity of startup ecosystems, play a more decisive role in shaping demand for technical specialists. Nevertheless, professional networks also affect labor market dynamics and career trajectories of engineers and programmers (Guerra & Mohnen [26]).

The scientific novelty of the research lies in substantiating an economic approach to evaluating technical recruiting in innovative companies under conditions of venture financing by linking recruiting efficiency with the development of startup ecosystems, the scale of venture capital, and the demand for highly qualified technical specialists. The analytical approach is improved through the integration of international statistical and analytical sources, which allowed combining indicators of startup ecosystem development, venture financing, high-tech employment, and demand for technical professions within a unified analytical framework.

The practical significance of the results lies in their potential application by startup founders, managers of innovative companies, HR departments, and venture investors when planning technical hiring strategies. The findings may support more informed recruitment decisions, the strategic formation of technical teams, and the assessment of startup scaling potential, as well as contribute to the development of innovation ecosystems and programs for training technical specialists.

Conclusions

It was established that the development of startup ecosystems and the growth of venture financing in the European Union and North America during 2019–2024 were accompanied by increasing demand for technical specialists in the high-technology sector. Investment growth in technology startups stimulates company scaling and increases the need for software engineers, data analysts, and other technical professionals.

It was determined that the key economic factors of technical recruiting effectiveness include the level of startup ecosystem development, the scale of venture financing, competition between technology

companies for talent, and structural characteristics of the labor market for highly qualified specialists. Together, these factors shape the economic environment of technical hiring in innovative companies.

It was generalized that evaluating technical recruiting effectiveness requires a set of economic indicators, including hiring costs, the speed of closing technical vacancies, the availability of technical specialists in the labor market, and the level of competition for highly qualified personnel.

It was confirmed that under conditions of digital transformation technical recruiting acquires strategic importance, since the effectiveness of attracting technical specialists influences the pace of startup scaling, the development of technological products, and companies' competitiveness in the high-technology sector.

It was established that the interaction of innovation ecosystem development, availability of technical talent, and investment activity forms economic conditions in which technical recruiting becomes an important factor of innovative company performance in venture-financed environments.

Prospects for further research are related to deeper analysis of economic mechanisms of technical recruiting at the level of individual innovative companies and to the development of more detailed models for evaluating the effectiveness of attracting technical specialists considering sectoral characteristics and different stages of startup development.

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